

1 **Woodland Mediterranean birds can resist a**
2 **dry extreme cold wave**

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8 Running title: **Bird resistance to extreme cold events**

9

10 **Abstract** The ecological consequences of climate extreme events are still poorly
11 understood, especially those related to cold episodes. Winter cold spells might imperil
12 the energy balance of small passerines, thus compromising their survivorship. Here we
13 analyze how the abundance and habitat use of three tree-gleaning passerine species
14 wintering in a montane oakwood of central Spain at ca. 1300 m a.s.l. was influenced by
15 the cold wave that hit Europe in February 2012. We monitored temperature, wind and
16 the relative abundance of great tit *Parus major*, blue tit *Cyanistes caeruleus* and long-
17 tailed tit *Aegithalos caudatus* in 15 plots throughout three periods: before, during and
18 after the cold wave. Our results clearly rule out widespread mortality and temporal
19 migration of the studied passerine populations, as the abundance of these species did not
20 diminish during the cold wave. Moreover, the species usually foraging higher in the tree
21 canopy -and thus more exposed to wind- moved to the less windy woodland plots (long-
22 tailed tit) and reduced their foraging height above ground during the cold wave (long-
23 tailed tit and blue tit), probably to mitigate the deleterious effects of wind chill.
24 Therefore, these forest birds were able to cope with a dry cold wave that was
25 statistically extreme in terms of temperature and wind chill, according to the historic
26 climate records of the region. It seems that, at least when foraging substrates are not
27 heavily covered by snow or ice, Mediterranean birds can resist an extreme cold wave.

28

29 **Keywords:** *Cold wave · Harsh weather · Mediterranean oakwoods · Temperature · Tree-*
30 *gleaning birds · Wind chill*

31

32 **Introduction**

33 Assessing the ecological effects of extreme climate events poses a major
34 challenge because of the nature of such events: they are short, rare, not very predictable,
35 and highly dependent on the context. The extremeness of a climatic event must be
36 defined based on the historic climate record, because the ecological response of species
37 may depend on what the population has experienced in the past (Jentsch, 2006; Jentsch
38 et al., 2007; Gutschick et al., 2010; Smith, 2011a; b). The ecological responses to
39 statistically extreme climatic conditions have been approached through both
40 experiments and opportunistic observational studies. A number of experiments show a
41 surprising lack of strong ecological responses (Smith, 2011a and references therein), but
42 sadly negative results are less often reported in observational studies (but see Jiguet et
43 al., 2011). This may reflect a biased motivation of scientists for episodes with obvious
44 ecological responses (e.g., widespread mortality of a species; Smith, 2011a) or
45 difficulties publishing negative results (Fanelli, 2012). However, this research discipline
46 may benefit from combining the results obtained from both extreme events and
47 “normal” natural situations to disentangle the triggers of the responses in each system.

48 Ecological responses to climate extremes may range from temporal migration of
49 individuals, to population crashes, to long-term changes in community structure or
50 ecosystem function (see reviews of Jiguet et al., 2011 and Smith, 2011b, and references
51 therein). In a global warming scenario, the emphasis is rarely put on extreme cold
52 events (e.g., Jentsch and Beierkuhnlein, 2008; Cattiaux et al., 2013). Nevertheless,
53 severe cold weather might imperil the energy balance of wintering small passerines
54 beyond normal thresholds. At temperate latitudes, birds have to cope with winter
55 temperatures well below their thermoneutral zone (Calder and King, 1974; Kendeigh et
56 al., 1977), and their metabolic costs of thermoregulation increase with decreasing

57 temperatures and increasing wind speeds (e.g., Wood and Lustick, 1989; Wolf and
58 Walsberg, 1996; Wolf et al., 2000). Accordingly, these species may select the warmest
59 areas at the landscape scale to overwinter in order to minimize thermoregulation costs
60 (e.g., Canterbury, 2002; Meehan et al., 2004; Evans et al., 2006; La Sorte et al., 2009;
61 Carrascal et al., 2001; 2012).

62 Here we analyze the resistance of three resident woodland passerines, with a
63 broad distribution in Europe, facing a cold wave that hit Europe in February 2012, by
64 measuring their changes in abundance, local distribution and habitat use. The studied
65 species do not store food during winter and belong to a tree-gleaning guild of the
66 montane areas of the Iberian Peninsula. We postulate three possible scenarios of
67 population response to this dry extreme cold wave (Figure 1). First, the cold wave may
68 not negatively affect local abundance of species, because birds present adaptations to
69 cope with severe weather at a local scale (e.g., changes in foraging behavior and habitat
70 use), and these conditions may not be extreme for these species in the context of their
71 total geographic distribution (i.e., similar low winter temperatures in central and
72 northern Europe). In this case, the relative abundance of species may not diminish with
73 the arrival of the cold wave. Second, the cold wave should impose a temporal migration
74 of part of or the whole wintering populations, which would return after the end of the
75 cold wave to their winter territories and restore normal abundance levels. And third, the
76 cold wave could provoke widespread population mortality, so local abundance would
77 decrease during the cold wave but would not recover to reach previous levels
78 afterwards. The two last predictions assume that Mediterranean populations present a
79 reduction in the level of adaptation to extreme cold compared with more northern and
80 central Europe populations. To test these hypotheses, we monitored local abundance of
81 birds before, during and after the dry cold wave, measuring the local environmental

82 conditions in terms of temperature, wind speed and wind chill. We also analyzed the
83 environmental determinants of the spatial variation in abundance within the study area
84 during the cold wave, to detect if birds move to the warmer and less windy forest
85 patches to mitigate the deleterious effects of wind chill. Finally, we analyzed whether
86 these species vary their height above ground as a way to behaviorally minimize the
87 effects of wind chill *in situ*.

88

89

90 **Methods**

91 **Study area**

92 Field work was conducted in an oakwood located in Navacerrada (40.725°N,
93 4.033°W; Sierra de Guadarrama, Central Spain). The study area is a ca. 3 km² mosaic of
94 open and dense patches of a monospecific forest of *Quercus pyrenaica* (a marcescent
95 species typical of southwestern Mediterranean mountains), mainly dominated by young
96 trees of 6-14 m. The rugged terrain comprises a high heterogeneity of cardinal
97 orientations, which means a broad variation in sun radiation incidence and in the
98 protection from dominant winds, and thus in microclimate conditions. Altitude ranges
99 between 1200 and 1360 m a.s.l. Landscape surrounding the study area within a radius of
100 20 km is mainly dominated by pine forests of *Pinus sylvestris* and shrublands of *Cistus*
101 *ladanifer* above 1300 m a.s.l., and by parklands of holm oak (*Quercus rotundifolia*) and
102 ash (*Fraxinus angustifolia*), pastures and urban areas below 1200 m a.s.l. The nearest
103 oakwood larger than 1 km² is located 20 km downslope at 960-1100 m a.s.l. Nest boxes
104 have not been available in the whole study area since 2004 (i.e., birds could not make
105 use of artificial roosting places).

106 The climate is continental cold Mediterranean, with dry and hot summers and
107 abundant snowfall and frost in winter. For more details on vegetation structure,
108 temperature and bird communities of these forests in Central Spain see Seoane et al.
109 (2013).

110

111 **Study period**

112 Three study periods were defined: mild-weather period prior to the cold wave
113 (hereafter Before CW; sampled on 3, 9, 10, 11 January 2012), cold wave (CW; 2, 3, 4, 8
114 February 2012), and mild-weather period after the cold wave (After CW; 17, 18, 22, 23,
115 24 February 2012). Our study design ensured that there were no significant differences
116 among plots in average sampling time in the three study periods ($p > 0.96$ in the three
117 one-way ANOVAs).

118

119 **Focal species**

120 The focal species were the most abundant of the tree-gleaning guild of the
121 mountainous oakwoods of Central Spain (Carrascal et al., 1987): *Parus major major*
122 (great tit), *Cyanistes caeruleus oligastrae* (blue tit) and *Aegithalos caudatus irbii* (long-
123 tailed tit). They are residents and relatively abundant throughout the winter in the oak
124 forests of the Guadarrama mountains (Carrascal and Díaz, 2006). These small-sized
125 species mainly forage on the twigs and small branches of trees, although they can also
126 use the forest floor for foraging (especially the great tit; Carrascal et al. 1987). The
127 study was centered in these species because passerines foraging in small branches are
128 more severely affected by low temperatures and high wind speed than those foraging on
129 the ground or on the trunks of trees (Grubb, 1975). Moreover, they do not store food, so
130 they rely only on body reserves to overcome severe periods of inclement weather

131 (Perrins, 1979). Other small tree-gleaning species were present in the study area, but
132 were too scarce to obtain a large and representative sample to measure abundance
133 changes among study periods of different weather (lesser spotted woodpecker,
134 *Dendrocopos minor*, nuthatch, *Sitta europaea*, short-toed treecreeper, *Certhia*
135 *brachydactyla*).

136 Although these species can experience latitudinal and local altitudinal
137 movements to avoid harsh weather in winter (Perrins, 1979; Cramp, 1998), they are
138 highly sedentary during winter in central Spain according to data obtained from the
139 Spanish Centro de Migración de Aves (<http://www.anillamientoseo.org>) using ring
140 recoveries obtained during the last 30 years (data for 640 *P. major*, 640 *C. caeruleus*
141 and 247 *A. caudatus* birds recaptured in Madrid province). Only 0.5% of great tits and
142 1.2% of blue tits were recaptured in different ringing stations located farther than 1 km
143 during the same autumn-winter (December to February), moving a maximum of 22 km
144 and an average of 7.5 km for blue tits (n=8) and 10.7 km for great tits (n=3). No
145 recoveries of long-tailed tits were made outside the ringing stations within the same
146 autumn-winter period. These data for the three study species in Central Spain are very
147 similar to those recorded in northeastern Iberian Peninsula (Herrando et al. 2011). We
148 think that there is a very remote probability of birds belonging to the three focal species
149 coming to the study area from higher altitudes during the cold spell, considering that (1)
150 these species are almost absent from the nearby *Pinus sylvestris* pine forests found
151 upslope (Carrascal et al. 1987), and (2) there are no deciduous forests at higher altitudes
152 close to our study area (the nearest large oakwood located at higher altitude is 21 km
153 away crossing several ridges of higher altitude).

154

155 **Statistical characterization of the cold wave in February 2012**

156 The meteorological characteristics of the cold wave studied here were compared
157 with the daily historical record from the period 1946-2012 (data from the nearby
158 meteorological station in Navacerrada Pass, located at 7 km from the study area, 1894m,
159 AEMET; n = 24193 days for temperature data; n = 18843 days for wind data). Cold
160 days were defined as those with minimum temperatures below the long-term 5th
161 percentile of daily minimum temperatures, or wind chill temperatures below the long-
162 term 5th percentile of daily wind chill temperatures (analogous to Della-Marta et al.
163 [2007] criterion to define hot days).

164 The month of February 2012 was the coldest February in Spain since 1956 (i.e.,
165 the one with the lowest daily averages of minimum temperatures in 56 years). We focus
166 on a cold wave of 12 days, which included three 'sub-waves' of three consecutive cold
167 days each (with daily minimum temperatures below the long-term 5th percentile of
168 daily minimum temperatures). Three cold days in a row cannot be considered a
169 statistically extreme event in the study area (where the upper 5th percentile of number
170 of consecutive cold days is five). However, temperatures were very low during the
171 whole cold wave and, during this 12-day period, the mean of the minimum (-11.6 °C at
172 Navacerrada Pass, 1894 m a.s.l.), average (-8.3 °C), and maximum (-5 °C) temperatures
173 were all within the lower 5th percentile of historical records (-10 °C, -8 °C and -5 °C,
174 respectively).

175 During the 12 days, average wind speed was 4.9 m/s (data for 10 days with wind
176 records), which is above the upper quartile of historically-recorded average wind speeds
177 (4.7 m/s). The extreme low temperatures coupled with these relatively strong winds
178 resulted in an average wind chill temperature (WCT; following Osczevski and
179 Bluestein, 2005) of -15.3 °C, which is well below the lower historical 5th percentile (-
180 11.7 °C). During the cold wave there were at least four cold days in a row considering

181 the WCT (days with WCT below the lower historical 5th percentile). Four cold days
182 considering WCT is a statistical extreme event in the study area (where the upper 5th
183 percentile of number of consecutive cold days is four). In addition, we sampled during
184 the windiest days of the cold wave, with an average wind speed of 6.4 m/s and an
185 average WCT of -19.7 °C. The cold wave in the area was not accompanied by heavy
186 precipitation (average of 5 mm for the 12 days; 1.5 mm for sampling days in
187 Navacerrada Pass). Sun was shining 28% of the time, it was snowing lightly 42% of
188 time, and snow cover and depth on the ground was, on average, 55% and 2.5 cm
189 (measurements obtained during the sampling of woodland plots). Therefore, we
190 consider that it was a relatively dry period.

191

192 **Bird censuses, habitat structure and temperature and wind measurements**

193 We measured local bird abundance using point count stations lasting 5 min,
194 recording all birds heard or seen within a 25 m radius (0.19 ha). The census began upon
195 arrival at the center of each plot, and continued following the same protocol in all
196 samples: we walked very slowly within the area of the census plot over an imaginary
197 circumference of radius 12.5 m. By means of this approach we aimed to maximize the
198 detection probability of the birds within the census plot even under windy or snowy
199 circumstances. Thus, our census method does not intend to measure exact bird densities
200 (i.e., birds / ha), but to obtain a measure of habitat use in different woodland plots under
201 different weather conditions. Upon detection of each bird, we also estimated its height
202 above ground as a measure of habitat use. After the census, we walked at a brisk pace in
203 order to reach the following sampling point as soon as possible so as to minimize the
204 probability of sampling the same birds in two consecutive plots (i.e., we moved faster
205 than the study species usually do while moving in the forest).

206 The two authors carried out the censuses. Fifteen woodland plots of 25 m radius
207 were established within the study area. Plots were separated by at least 250 m. We
208 followed an a priori planned protocol of sequential sampling in order to obtain a
209 completely overlapping distribution of the time of the day when the 15 plots were
210 sampled. To accomplish this goal, we began each sampling day with a different
211 sequence of contiguous plots (e.g., 1, 2, ... 14, 15; 5, 6, ... 15, 1, ... 4; etc). Sampling
212 began at 9:00 h and ended at 17:00 h GMT. Four censuses per plot were carried out
213 before the cold wave (Before CW), seven during the cold wave (COLD WAVE) and ten
214 after it (After CW).

215 Within each census plot, we sampled two vegetation structure variables related
216 to maturity and density of the oakwood plot: average height of trees and number of
217 trunks with a diameter larger than 10 cm at breast level. Average oak height was 10.2 m
218 (range: 6-14; sd = 2.7) while average oak density was 146 trees / 0.19 ha (range: 62-
219 303; sd = 68.9). All vegetation structure measurements were obtained by the same
220 person within the same sampling day (LMC).

221 To describe local fine-grained variation in winter air temperatures, one
222 temperature logger (Onset HOBO Pendant, accuracy 0.47 °C) was set in each oakwood
223 plot. Loggers were placed on trunks, oriented to the north and at approximately 1.5 m
224 above ground. Data loggers recorded air temperature every 5 min from 01 January to 29
225 February 2012. Thus, we could link the moment of the census of each woodland plot to
226 the prevailing temperature while sampling (using the nearest temperature record to the
227 time when the census began). Wind speed during the census was measured as the
228 average of two wind measurements obtained with a portable handheld meter during 30
229 seconds (Ventix Thermo-Anemometer 8908); one 30 seconds before the beginning of

230 the census, and another immediately after the end of the 5 min census. For each 30-sec
231 sampling period we obtained the maximum registered wind speed.

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236 **Data analyses**

237 Due to logistic limitations we could not mark the study population for individual
238 identification. However, we estimate that our study area of ca. 3 km² may host several
239 hundred individuals of each species, considering that the average abundance of the
240 studied species ranges from 8.3 to 14.5 birds · 10 ha⁻¹ in the oakwoods of Central Spain
241 (Carrascal and Díaz, 2006). This high number of birds reduces, although it does not
242 eliminate, the risk of pseudo-replication, and thus type I error inflation. Therefore, we
243 built null statistical distributions using Monte Carlo analyses to estimate proper
244 significance levels in data analyses (Davison and Hinkley, 2007).

245 To test the hypotheses in Figure 1, local abundance of birds before the cold wave
246 (B-CW), during the cold wave (CW) and after it (A-CW) were compared using t-tests.
247 First, we obtained the t-test statistics for each species comparing the averages of the 15
248 woodland plots in B-CW vs. CW, and in CW vs. A-CW. Second, a randomization
249 process was carried out maintaining the data within each plot (i.e., the values of the
250 average number of birds recorded in [B-CW / CW] and [CW / A-CW]). The aim of this
251 randomization procedure was to preserve the spatial structure of the data, accounting for
252 the spatial autocorrelation of the data and for the possible pseudoreplication derived
253 from the fact that the same individual bird may be present in more than one woodland
254 plot on different days. Third, the t-tests were carried out considering the randomized

255 data for each species in the B-CW vs. CW, and CW vs. A-CW comparisons, thus
256 obtaining a null t statistic; this process was repeated 9,999 times. And fourth, the actual
257 figures of the t statistic testing B-CW vs. CW, and CW vs. A-CW were compared with
258 9,999 null t values obtained. Significance of t-tests was estimated considering the
259 position of these true t statistics within the null distribution of t figures, by means of the
260 percentiles using a two-tailed approach.

261 We also analyzed the environmental determinants of the spatial variation in
262 abundance within the study area during the cold wave to detect if individuals move to
263 the warmer and less windy forest patches to mitigate the deleterious effects of the cold
264 wave. The influence of temperature, maximum wind speed and habitat variables on bird
265 habitat use during the cold weather period was analyzed by means of multiple
266 regression. Average number of birds per woodland plot was the response variable, while
267 average temperature, maximum wind speed, oak height and oak density were the
268 predictors. A multiple regression was carried out with the data for each species
269 separately. The significance of partial regression coefficients was estimated by means of
270 Monte Carlo analyses. A randomization process was carried out bootstrapping the data
271 on bird abundance for each plot. With the bootstrapped data, the same multiple
272 regression analyses (one per species) were carried out, obtaining null partial regression
273 coefficients; this process was repeated 9,999 times. The actual figures of the partial
274 regression coefficients were compared with the 9,999 null values obtained. Significance
275 of partial regression coefficients were estimated considering the position of the true
276 coefficients within the null distribution by means of the percentiles using a two-tailed
277 approach. Analyses were carried out using the Resampling and Monte Carlo functions
278 of «Pop Tools 3.0» (<http://www.cse.csiro.au/poptools/>) within MicroSoft-Excel 2010.

279

280 **Results**

281 **Temperature and wind at sampling plots**

282 Temperature measured locally during sampling at the 15 woodland plots fell an
283 average of 12.9 °C (from 9.1 °C to -3.8 °C) from the previous mild-weather to the cold
284 wave period (Figure 2). After the cold wave it raised 14.2 °C to reach an average of 10.4
285 °C. Wind speed increased an average of 4.21 m s⁻¹ (from 0.83 m s⁻¹ to 5.04 m s⁻¹) from
286 the previous mild-weather period to the cold wave period, and decreased a similar
287 amount after the cold wave to an average of 1.13 m s⁻¹.

288 The cold wave reduced the spatial variation in the average temperatures among
289 woodland plots (i.e., difference between the warmest and the coldest plots), from a
290 range of 5.6 °C in the previous mild-weather sampling period to 2.7 °C during the cold
291 wave. Nevertheless, the variation in average wind speed among plots was higher during
292 the cold wave: the range between the windiest and the least windy plot increased from
293 0.96 m s⁻¹ in the previous mild-weather sampling period to 4.46 m s⁻¹ during the cold
294 wave. Nearly identical results are obtained comparing the spatial heterogeneity in
295 temperature and wind speed between the cold wave period and the posterior “normal”
296 period (not presented for the sake of brevity).

297

298 **Temporal and spatial variation in relative abundance of birds regarding the cold** 299 **wave**

300 The relative abundance of the three species during the cold wave did not change
301 with respect to previous mild conditions. However, bird abundance increased after the
302 cold wave for all species, reaching statistical significance for blue and great tits (Figure
303 3 and Table 1).

304 Habitat use by *A. caudatus* and *C. caeruleus* changed significantly during the
305 cold wave (Table 2). Both species forage at lower positions in the vertical axis of the
306 forest, by reducing by one half the average height above ground during the normal
307 periods. The height above ground of *P. major* during mild winter conditions was much
308 lower than that of the other species, and did not significantly change during the cold
309 wave.

310 The spatial variation of abundance within the forest during the cold wave was
311 not tightly related to local temperature or wind speed, after controlling for habitat
312 structure regarding oak height and density (Table 3). Only the relative abundance of the
313 long-tailed tit was significantly and negatively affected by wind speed; i.e., the long-
314 tailed tit preferred woodland areas with lower wind speed. Vegetation structure had no
315 significant partial effects on bird abundance, probably due to the low maturity of the
316 studied oakwood (see Methods) and the relatively low heterogeneity of oak height
317 (coefficient of variation, $CV = 26.5\%$) and oak density ($CV = 47.2\%$).

318

319 **Discussion**

320 Woodland Mediterranean birds were able to cope with a winter dry cold spell
321 that was statistically extreme in terms of the historical climate records of the region
322 according to measurements of temperature, wind speed or wind chill. Our results clearly
323 rule out widespread mortality and temporal migration of the studied passerine
324 populations and emphasize the winter residency of blue, great and long-tailed tits in
325 Mediterranean oakwoods (Tellería et al., 1999).

326 Populations may have a high ability to surpass periodic extreme events of cold
327 weather, especially in habitats subjected to very high seasonal climatic fluctuations like
328 the Mediterranean (average temperatures from 22°C in summer to -5°C in winter in

329 Iberian oakwoods of *Quercus pyrenaica*; Costa et al., 1998). Moreover, cold spells
330 might be less damaging in the southern part of the distribution range of these Palearctic
331 species, where the extended day length, the milder average temperatures and the higher
332 food availability may facilitate survivorship with respect to higher latitudes (Root,
333 1988; 2000).

334 Certain combinations of climate extremes might be necessary to evoke more
335 extreme ecological responses than those found here (Smith, 2011b). In this study, a dry
336 cold spell characterized by extreme low temperatures and strong wind speeds on a
337 regional basis, and a low amount of precipitation, was not enough to trigger a decrease
338 in species abundance derived from temporal migration or mortality. Snow cover and ice
339 impede access to ground resources, and, under freezing temperatures, water from mist,
340 rain or snow adhere to branches impeding access to food (Brotons, 1997; Nakamura and
341 Shindo, 2001). Robinson et al. (2007) found that the consecutive number of snow days
342 and cold-wet days were the variables most affecting survival of British Great and Blue
343 tits, respectively. Moreover, Carrascal (1988) found that a winter snow storm provoked
344 a significant decrease in the abundance and species richness of the avian community of
345 a subalpine pinewood located in the same region, where a very broad altitudinal
346 gradient of continuous pinewoods let the birds migrate to lower altitudes. Although
347 environmental temperatures in the Carrascal (1988) study were considerably higher than
348 those registered in this study (average of -0.5 °C vs -3.8 °C, in the cold wave period of
349 our study), there was a complete coverage of snow and ice on the ground, bushes and
350 trees, which may have triggered the temporal migration of most branch- and foliage-
351 gleaning birds along the altitudinal gradient of the mountain range. Nevertheless, snow
352 cover and thickness was low in our study and ice crust did not affect the branches of the
353 oaks in a generalized and widespread way. The comparison of these two studies (very

354 cold, windy and relatively dry weather vs. widespread cover of a thick layer of snow
355 and ice-crust with less cold temperatures) points out that the role of temperature will be
356 of lower importance considering that birds can withstand severe cold periods if enough
357 food is available and its access is not completely limited (Newton, 1980; Jenni, 1987).

358 The significant increase in abundance shown from the cold wave to the
359 following milder period is an unexpected result impossible to explain according to the
360 highly improbable migration of the studied species from the mountain scrublands and
361 pineforests located at higher altitudes where these species are very scarce or absent
362 (Carrascal et al., 1987; 2002). The increase in abundance of the three focal species
363 immediately after the cold spell may reflect the steady increase in population abundance
364 usually registered in these forests towards the following breeding season. At these
365 latitudes, an important proportion of resident woodland birds inhabiting mountain areas
366 move to lower areas at the beginning of the autumn to spend the winter under milder
367 winter conditions, and move back upslope to their breeding grounds at the end of winter
368 (Cramp, 1998). This pattern of local movements from higher altitudes to lower altitudes
369 in mountain areas at the beginning of the autumn, and from woodlands in valleys to
370 high altitude forests, is probably responsible for the seasonal changes in bird abundance
371 in Central Spain (e.g., Sánchez, 1991), and is the most parsimonious explanation for the
372 steady increase in the abundance of tits in the study region from midwinter as spring
373 approaches (O. Gordo, J.J. Sanz and L.M. Carrascal pers. obs.). Early residence in
374 future breeding grounds may promote an early laying date, which is usually related to
375 reproductive success (Norris, 1993), as later clutches tend to be smaller, and earlier-
376 fledged young tend to be heavier and have higher recruitment probabilities (e.g.,
377 Verboven and Visser, 1998; Potti, 2009). In this context, the cold wave could have

378 meant a temporal slowdown of this steady increase in abundance, because bird numbers
379 remained unchanged between the cold spell and the prior normal periods (see Table 1).

380 The harshness of a cold spell can be lessened by a temporal migration towards
381 lower altitudes with ameliorated weather conditions (Perrins, 1979). In this case, birds
382 could have moved to small deciduous forest patches, parklands and villages found 100-
383 300 m below. However, we found no evidence of such altitudinal migration. Escaping
384 to unknown areas implies a high risk considering the energy investment on small-scale
385 migration, and the uncertainty related to weather conditions, the availability of food
386 resources and competition with resident birds at the new areas (Senar and Borrás, 2004).
387 These disadvantages may have prevented resident birds from moving away from their
388 regular foraging areas. Future studies with marked individuals would help to further
389 understand to what extent resident woodland birds move when facing unexpected short
390 periods of inclement weather.

391 Alternatively, the three study species may have resisted the cold wave by
392 ameliorating the negative consequences of the harsh weather *in situ* through various
393 behavioral strategies. First, birds may selectively move locally within the forest area,
394 searching for woodland patches where the topography and the vegetation offer higher
395 temperatures and a greater shelter from wind (Grubb, 1977; Petit, 1989; Dolby and
396 Grubb, 1999). We indeed found that the long-tailed tit, the species that mainly forages
397 in the most pliable substrates of deciduous trees (Carrascal et al., 1987), avoided the
398 windiest plots during the cold wave (Table 3), although this search for locally milder
399 weather conditions was not shown by the other two tit species (that make an intense use
400 of the inner parts of the oaks and even forage on the ground). One explanation for the
401 very low importance of local movements seeking better thermal conditions is that
402 temperature and wind conditions were much homogenized throughout the study area

403 during the cold wave, limiting the potential benefit of spatial redistribution. This,
404 together with the uncertainties of displacements to other locations where competition
405 with other resident birds may increase, might prevent the role of local movements in
406 escaping from severe weather conditions. On the other hand, birds may have buffered
407 the deleterious effects of wind chill locally by changing their foraging behavior, shifting
408 to more sheltered, lower and inner parts of trees (Grubb, 1975; 1977; see Carrascal,
409 1987 for forests in Central Spain). Indeed we found that the two species that mainly
410 forage at higher parts within trees, and thus are more exposed to wind (i.e., *A. caudatus*
411 and *C. caeruleus*), reduced their average height above ground during the cold wave to
412 almost half the height under normal circumstances (Table 2).

413 In summary, birds wintering in a montane forest of cold Mediterranean climate
414 were able to resist an extreme dry cold wave, and showed no evidence of migration or
415 widespread local mortality. They probably buffered the deleterious effect of wind chill
416 by moving to the most protected forest patches and by reducing their foraging height
417 within the tree canopy.

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426

427

428 **References**

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553

554 **Figure 1.** Three possible scenarios of response of bird populations to the studied cold
555 wave (grey area). From top to bottom: (1) the cold wave did not affect species
556 abundance at all, (2) it promoted a temporal downslope migration of individuals, or (3)
557 it provoked a widespread mortality of the population. Winter dates go from 1st January
558 to 28th February.

559

560 **Figure 2.** Changes in temperature and wind speed during the cold wave, compared with
561 previous and post-sampling periods (average \pm one standard error). Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
562 and maximum wind speed ($\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) were registered on several occasions during sampling
563 and averaged per plot and sampling period (see Methods). Sample size is 15 plots. X-
564 axis shows the average sampling date of each period.

565

566 **Figure 3.** Abundance of birds during the cold wave, compared with previous and post-
567 sampling periods. Abundance measures the average number of individuals (\pm one SE)
568 of *Aegithalos caudatus* (Ac), *Cyanistes caeruleus* (Cc) and *Parus major* (Pm) found in
569 censuses of 5 min in 15 plots of 0.19 ha. Sample size is 15 plots. X-axis shows the
570 average sampling date of each period.

571

572 **Table 1.** Average changes in the abundance of the three species between periods.
 573 Positive figures are increases in abundance. Before CW: Mild-weather period prior to
 574 the cold wave; CW: Cold wave; After CW: Mild-weather period after the cold wave. P-
 575 values correspond to two-tailed t tests. See also Figure 3.

576

	Before CW - CW		CW - After CW	
	difference	p	difference	p
577 <i>Aegithalos caudatus</i>	0.00	0.929	0.16	0.173
578 <i>Cyanistes caeruleus</i>	0.01	0.947	0.24	0.003
579 <i>Parus major</i>	0.03	0.660	0.37	0.000

582

583

584

585 **Table 2.** Bird height above ground (m) during the cold wave and during the normal
 586 winter periods (i.e., “Before CW” plus “After CW”). Sample sizes (N) refer to different
 587 foraging birds (one sample per bird and per plot). Z and p: results from Mann-Whitney
 588 U tests.

589

	COLD WAVE			MILD WINTER			Z	p
	N	mean	sd	N	mean	sd		
<i>Aegithalos caudatus</i>	12	3.5	2.7	25	6.4	3.8	2.450	0.014
<i>Cyanistes caeruleus</i>	24	4.0	2.6	46	7.5	4.3	3.613	<0.001
<i>Parus major</i>	31	2.6	2.5	50	2.9	2.6	0.763	0.445

590

591 **Table 3.** Regression model on the influence of environmental factors on the abundance
 592 of *Aegithalos caudatus*, *Cyanistes caeruleus* and *Parus major* during the cold wave.
 593 Figures are partial regression coefficients (*b*) of tree height, density of trees with dbh >
 594 10 cm, average temperature and maximum wind speed. P-values are two-tailed tests;
 595 significant tests are in bold type.

596

	<i>A. caudatus</i>		<i>C. caeruleus</i>		<i>P. major</i>	
	<i>b</i>	p	<i>b</i>	p	<i>b</i>	p
599 Tree height	0.004	0.916	0.020	0.429	0.017	0.432
600 # trees > 10 cm dbh	0.001	0.666	0.001	0.137	0.001	0.144
601 Average temperature (°C)	-0.013	0.934	-0.076	0.448	0.065	0.478
602 Maximum wind speed (ms-1)	-0.176	0.045	-0.048	0.398	-0.009	0.854

603

